

Geolab SURE

Centrifuge tests

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Executive Summary

This document summarizes the planning, implementation, and main outcomes of the GEOLAB Transnational Access project SURE, carried out at the Universite Gustave Eiffel's geotechnical centrifuge facilities and coordinated by ProRail, Arcadis, Deltares, and Delft University of Technology.

The main goal of SURE is to investigate the effect of an increased use of railways on the stability of a section of embankment founded on soft soil, as typically encountered within the Netherlands infrastructure. The project included four separate centrifuge tests, including two models of undrained monotonic loading of the embankment section until failure, and two additional models of cyclic loading resembling typical and increased train passages over the embankment section.

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Contents

Executive Summary	3
Contents	4
Nomenclature	5
1 Introduction	7
1.1 General Context	7
1.2 Purpose of SURE	7
2 Experimental Methodology	8
2.1 Prototype Condition in SURE	8
2.2 Centrifuge Scaling Interpretation	9
2.3 Experimental Campaign	9
2.3.1 Experimental Setup	9
2.3.2 Sample Preparation and Material Properties	10
2.3.3 Experimental Protocol	11
2.3.4 Data Management Protocol	12
2.3.5 Remarks on Pore-pressure transducer locations	12
3 Test 1 (Container 1)	13
3.1 General Overview	13
3.2 Evolution of <i>FA</i> , <i>dL</i> , <i>R</i> , and Pore-water pressures	13
3.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing	14
3.4 Failure Mechanism	15
4 Test 2 (Container 2)	17
4.1 General Overview	17
4.2 Evolution of <i>FA</i> , <i>dL</i> , <i>R</i> , and Pore-water pressures	17
4.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing	18
4.4 Failure Mechanism	19
5 Test 3 (Container 3)	22
5.1 General Overview	22
5.1.1 Cyclic Loading Sequences	22
5.2 Evolution of <i>FA</i> , <i>dL</i> , <i>R</i> , and Pore-water pressures	23
5.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing	24
5.4 Failure Mechanism	25
5.6 Additional Measurements	27
5.6.1 Post-failure water contents on Speswhite kaolin	27
6 Test 4 (Container 4)	28
6.1 General Overview	28
6.1.1 Cyclic Loading Sequences	28
6.2 Evolution of <i>FA</i> , <i>dL</i> , <i>R</i> , and Pore-water pressures	29
6.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing	30
6.4 Failure Mechanism	31
6.5 Additional Measurements	33
6.5.1 Post-failure water contents of Speswhite kaolin	33
6.5.2 Temperature evolution during flight on Test 4	34

Nomenclature

α	=	Scaling law for acceleration
A	=	Load amplitude
C_g	=	Coefficient of Gradation
C_u	=	Coefficient of Uniformity
CPT_i	=	Cone penetration test i
d_{50}	=	Grain size at which 50% of soil particles (by weight) are finer
d_{CPT}	=	Displacement of CPT probe during CPT probing
d_i	=	Displacement sensor i
e	=	Void ratio
e_i	=	Estimated void ratio of clay slurry
e_0	=	Estimated void ratio of foundation soil before spinning
e_{max}, e_{min}	=	Maximum and minimum void ratio
F_A	=	Force applied by actuator
F_{CPT}	=	Reaction force during CPT probing
G_s	=	Specific gravity
L	=	Scaling law for linear distances
LL	=	Liquid Limit
LVDT	=	Linear Variable Differential Transformer
N	=	Increment of centrifuge gravitational acceleration field relative to Earth's gravity
NNAE	=	National Network Analysis of Embankments
PPT_i	=	Pore pressure transducer i
RD	=	Relative density
RESET	=	Reliable Embankments for Safe Expansion in Rail Traffic
SURE	=	Stability under increased Usage of Railway Embankments
t	=	Time
\mathbf{t}	=	Scaling law for time
\mathbf{t}_{diff}	=	Scaling law for time in diffusion events
$Temp$	=	Temperature
v	=	Scaling law for kinematic velocity
\mathbf{v}_{diff}	=	Scaling law for velocity in diffusion events
w_c	=	Water content
\mathbf{X}	=	Scaling law for variable X – in bold fonts
X_m	=	Magnitude of variable X at the centrifuge model scale
X_p	=	Magnitude of variable X at the prototype scale
γ_{sat}	=	Saturated unit weight of foundation soil

- ρ = Scaling law for density
- σ = Scaling law for stress
- σ_p = Pre-consolidation Stress
- ϕ_c = Friction angle at critical state

1 Introduction

1.1 General Context

ProRail manages 7000 km of Dutch railway track built on approximately 3000 km of embankments. Many of these embankments are over a hundred years old and are constructed on very soft clay and peat layers. Over time, the weight of the trains has increased, and the use of railway tracks in terms of the number of train passages per hour has also increased.

To gain a better understanding of the impact of the increased rail traffic on the embankments and subsoil, ProRail launched the Embankment Programme in 2021. Part of this programme is the National Network Analysis of Embankments (NNAE), which includes Deltares, Arcadis, and three more engineering companies. The NNAE evaluates the stability of all railway embankments within ProRail's network. These assessments have shown that the stability of many embankments does not meet current guidelines and standards. However, most of these embankments appear stable under current use despite the need for additional maintenance in some locations where deformations are encountered and measured. It is noted that the NNAE's stability assessments are based on a stochastic subsoil model based on local geological knowledge and sparse, publicly available soil investigation data taken from the railway zones. This leads to approximately 10 potential stratification scenarios for the soil and corresponding soil parameters for stability analysis at each location. Nonetheless, it is suspected that the standards are cautious and relatively conservative as many aspects of the train loading and soil strength are not fully understood.

The growth in railway infrastructure usage is expected to continue in the coming years due to the continued search for environmentally sustainable transportation systems across the Netherlands and Europe. Therefore, a better understanding of the behaviour of Dutch railway embankments under current loading conditions and their potential changes for future loading scenarios is a primary need for ProRail and the engineering practice. As such, in addition to the NNAE, ProRail, Deltares and TU Delft started the RESET programme, which aims to enable a safe, accelerated increase of rail freight, frequency and traffic; optimise the scope of necessary embankment improvements and reduce construction costs; provide direct insight into the influence and consequences of climate change in the stability assessments; and identify unnecessary conservatism and improve the current guidelines for advanced embankment assessments. The results of SURE will be used as inputs to the RESET programme.

1.2 Purpose of SURE

The project "Stability under increased Usage of Railway Embankments", or SURE, is a Transnational Access project sponsored by GEOLAB (<https://project-geolab.eu/>). The goal of SURE was to investigate the effect of an increased use of railways on the stability of a section of embankment with a soft soil as a foundation, resembling a typical soil condition for railway embankments within the western part of the Netherlands network. The project used the centrifuge modelling technique and a series of small-scale models resembling the current railway use and a hypothetical future loading condition with increased train passages per hour. Reference experiments were also performed to evaluate the ultimate loading capacity of the system under undrained loading conditions.

2 Experimental Methodology

2.1 Prototype Condition in SURE

The general conditions assessed in this project comprised a 9-m-long control section consisting of a sandy embankment with dimensions of 7 m in width (measured at the top), 1 m in height, and an underlying soft clay layer with a thickness of 6 m. The embankment and foundation underlay a railway structure subjected to train passages with a design load of 35 kPa and travelling at a constant speed of 140 km/h, which results in a loading duration of nearly 5.5 seconds across the control section. This study evaluated the general response of the structure for two intensity loading conditions: a) a train passing the control section every 10 minutes, and b) a train passing the control section every 4 minutes. Figure 1 shows a general sketch of the prototype conditions proposed in SURE at the top figure. As shown, the control section extends sufficiently in width from the embankment's toe to the right to provide space for developing potential failure planes across the foundation soil. The bottom figure shows the prototype load of an eight-coach train together with the load approximation proposed for the centrifuge tests.

Figure 1. General prototype condition (top) and train loading (bottom).

2.2 Centrifuge Scaling Interpretation

The geotechnical centrifuge modelling technique uses a simulated increased gravitational acceleration field imposed in a small-scale model through radial acceleration to replicate stress levels similar to those typically encountered at a much larger scale in geotechnical infrastructure. The similarity between events and behaviours reproduced in the small-scale model in the centrifuge environment and those occurring on the field or at a larger scale, usually referred to as the prototype condition, is generally addressed through scaling laws. These scaling laws are typically presented for specific variables that best represent the system or the events modelled, and they are estimated as the ratio of the magnitude of a given variable in the small-scale model and that in the prototype. Then, a scaling law of $X = X_m/X_p$ exists for a given variable X . For clarity of the reader, scaling laws are presented in bold fonts in this document.

The fundamental scaling laws used in SURE result from the centrifuge experimental approach, including scaling for acceleration as $a = N$, linear distances as $L = N^{-1}$, and stresses as $\sigma = 1$. The latter considers that the same soil and pore fluid exists in both model and prototype (i.e., $\rho = 1$). Dimensional analysis of these variables leads to scaling laws for others, including area, volume, force, and velocities for kinematic events and diffusion problems. Further details on the derivation of scaling laws are widely available in the literature (e.g., Goodings 1982, Taylor 1994, lai et al. 2005, Garnier et al. 2007).

It is noted that the nature of the events modelled in SURE potentially leads to scaling conflicts in the time scale reproduced in the centrifuge models. The duration of the train passage across the control section can be interpreted as a kinematic event resulting from the train travelling at a constant speed between two points, which can be scaled to the small-scale model with $v = 1$. This allows for the estimation of the loading duration atop the embankment through $t = N^{-1}$. However, problems involving diffusion events, such as the dissipation of excess pore pressures in fine-grained soils, are scaled as $v_{diff} = N$ and $t_{diff} = N^{-2}$ (Taylor 1994). Since the loading conditions modelled in SURE are generally undrained and the strength of the foundation soil is strongly related to the excess pore pressures generated during loading and dissipated afterwards, the latter set of scaling laws was used for the experimental campaign. A summary of the scaling laws used is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of scaling laws relevant for SURE.

Variable	Scaling Factor	Variable	Scaling Factor
Acceleration	N	Force	N^2
Length	N^{-1}	Stress	1
Displacement	N^{-1}	Density	1
Time	N^{-1}	Time (consolidation)	N^{-2}
Velocity	1	Velocity (consolidation)	N

It is acknowledged that the approach proposed for SURE may only partially capture the behaviours expected to occur in the prototype condition due to, among others, the dynamic loading condition proposed. However, it must be highlighted that this approach also considers the physical and mechanical capabilities available during the execution of the experiments, and any experimental limitations should be considered while analysing the results.

2.3 Experimental Campaign

2.3.1 Experimental Setup

A customized experimental setup was designed to reproduce the prototype conditions in Figure 1 using a series of small-scale models under an increased gravitational acceleration field of 20 times Earth's gravity (i.e., $20g$) inside a 5.5 m-radius geotechnical centrifuge located at the University Gustave Eiffel Nantes. The target $20g$ was imposed for a radius of rotation at the surface of the clay surface. The experimental setup included a rectangular steel strongbox with an integrated transparent wall, a video camera recording at variable frames per second, and the small-scale models depicted in Figure 2. The inner planar area of the strongbox is 80 cm by 45 cm and its depth is 45 cm.

Figure 2. General model setup.

As indicated in Table 1, a scaling factor of $L = N$ was used to satisfy geometric similarity with the proposed prototype condition, resulting in the overall dimensions shown in Figure 2. A steel rigid plate attached to a servo-controlled vertical actuator was used to model the train passages. The rigid plate was 15 cm in width, resembling a prototype dimension of 3 m, and extended 45 cm in length (i.e., entire model length in y-axis) to satisfy a plane-strain condition.

The testing setup allowed continuous measurements of porewater pressures at five different locations within the foundation soil through a series of miniature pressure sensors, namely PPT_1 through PPT_5 . The vertical displacement of the rigid plate was monitored through the displacement of the actuator, d_{act} , and two additional linear variable differential transformers (LVDT) placed on each side of the plate, d_L and d_R . The increment in vertical load applied by the actuator to the embankment, F_A , was monitored through a load cell at the top of the rigid plate. Vertical deformations at the crest of the embankment, d_1 and d_2 , near the toe, d_3 , and at the free-field, d_4 , were also recorded using LVDTs. Temperature changes during flight were also recorded for a single experiment, as discussed in a later section.

2.3.2 Sample Preparation and Material Properties

The foundation soil used in this study was Speswhite kaolin clay, originating from Germany. The embankment was made of Fontainebleau sand, a uniformly graded, fine sand originating from France. Table 2 shows the general properties of these materials.

Table 2. General properties of Speswhite kaolin and Fontainebleau sand.

Speswhite Kaolin		Fontainebleau sand	
LL	66	d_{50}	0.21 mm
PI	31	Cu	1.47
G_s	2.584	Cg	??
$^a w_c$	44.7%	G_s	2.65
$^a e_0$	1.18	e_{max}	0.87
$^a \gamma_{sat}$	17.2 kN/m ³	e_{min}	0.53
$^a \sigma_p$	80 kPa	ϕ_c	31.5°

^a Estimated for the initial conditions after sample preparation

The foundation soil was prepared directly on the model strongbox by consolidating three layers of clay slurry with an initial water content of 99% (i.e., 1.5 times LL). This water content was selected to avoid any lumps of clay material during mixing. The approximated initial heights before consolidation of Layer 1, and Layers 2 and 3, as labelled in Figure 2, were 25 cm and 12.5 cm, respectively, resulting in an initial void ratio, e_i , of 2.6. Each layer was

consolidated using increments of surcharge load to a final pre-consolidation stress, σ_p , of 80 kPa. After consolidation, the foundation soil's water content, w_c , void ratio, e_0 , and saturated unit weight, γ_{sat} , were approximately 44.7%, 1.18, and 17.2 kN/m³, respectively. Specific gravity, G_s of the clay material was 2.584.

After the foundation soil was prepared, a cover layer of dry Fontainebleau sand was placed by dry pluviation to a final thickness of 5 cm and a dry unit weight of 16.3 kN/m³ ($e = 0.596$, $RD = 81\%$). The embankment was shaped afterwards by carefully removing the excess sand and trimming the slope to the final 2:1 (H:V) geometry.

2.3.3 Experimental Protocol

Figure 3 shows the general experimental protocol followed in SURE at the target g -level of $20g$. The stages performed are described below:

- Stage 1 consisted of an initial consolidation phase, which included applying and maintaining a constant load $F_A = 473$ N, resembling an approximate stress of 7 kPa. Assuming another 5 kPa of ballast in the sand (to 0.7 m below top of the track, refer RLN00414-1-V001), this resembles a total ballast stress of 12 kPa.
- Stage 2 consisted of the cyclic loading of the embankment under various combinations of frequency and load amplitude resembling the prototype conditions described in Figure 1.
- Stage 3 consisted of monotonic loading of the embankment until a maximum value of vertical displacement, d_A , of nearly 50 mm.
- Several Cone Penetration Tests, here referred to as CPT_i , were performed at various locations within the models, including the embankment section. The first CPT was performed at the end of stage 1 in the virgin soil, away from the embankment (i.e., toward the right side of the container in Figure 2). The probing was performed sufficiently away from the embankment to avoid any possible effect on the subsequent stages. The other CPT tests were performed after stage 3, at the end of the experiments, with the restriction of reducing the g -level to Earth's gravity and spinning back to $20g$ to allow for repositioning the CPT loading frame.

Additional information obtained before, during, and after the experiments in selected models included surface plots, determination of pore pressure sensor locations after loading, Shear Vane Tests, water content measurements, and temperature evolution during flight. The temperature evolution was only measured during the last test. It is noted that the first two tests were performed in February 2024 whereas the last two tests were performed in July 2024. The centrifuge chamber is not temperature conditioned, so temperature differences between the tests are expected. See section 6.5.2 Temperature evolution during flight on Test 4.

Figure 3 General overview of experimental protocol

A total of four tests were performed in SURE. Test 1 was conducted as an exploratory experiment and consisted of the monotonic “drained” loading of the embankment under variable displacement rates until failure. This experiment included Stage 1 without the ballast load, Stage 3, and additional CPT tests. Test 2 consisted of the monotonic loading under fully undrained conditions and comprised Stages 1 and 3, and various CPT tests. Tests 3 and 4 were used to evaluate the intensity loading conditions proposed and included all the stages described above. Details of each test are presented later in this report.

2.3.4 Data Management Protocol

As pointed out in Figure 2, a wide number of instruments and measurements were obtained during tests within SURE. Unprocessed data is generally provided by the host institution (i.e., UniEiffel) in ASCII format and using default labels for each instrument or data channel used in the experimental campaign. Since these default labels may have changed between tests or may not have been used in some experiments, this report uses unified variable nomenclature, as described in Table 3.

Table 3 Corresponding ASCII labeling in unprocessed datafiles

Measurement	Units	Channel Name on ASCII Files			
		Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4
$Time$	s	Temps 2 - Vitesse de mesure standard			
F_A	N	F58			
d_A	mm	Disp_SVH300_SSI CH=18			
d_L		D25		D54 CH=4	
d_R		D55 CH=5		D55 CH=5	
d_1		D59 CH=6		D25	
d_2		Not Used / Not Available		D59 CH=6	
d_3				D151 CH=7	
d_4		D54 CH=4		D37 CH=8	
PPT_1		kPa	P211 CH=7	P219	P218
PPT_2	P212 CH=8		P216 CH=8	P211 CH=10	P215 CH=10
PPT_3	P214 CH=10		P217 CH=9	P212	P216
PPT_4	P213 CH=9		P210 CH=7	P210 CH=9	P214 CH=9
PPT_5	P215		P218 CH=10	P213	P217
$Temp$	°C	Not Used / Not Available			Temp CH=16
F_{CPT}	daN = 10 N	F_Tbar	F_CPT	F_CPT CH=14	
d_{CPT}	mm	z_Tbar	z_CPT	Dep_CPT CH=15	

2.3.5 Remarks on Pore-pressure transducer locations

The initial position of the pore-pressure transducers PPT_1 to PPT_5 was maintained for all the tests performed in SURE as described in Figure 2. However, different aspects during the preparation and execution of the experiments may have caused displacements from the initial positions, including movements during the consolidation stages and/or displacements during the loading stages of the tests. Although a precise position of the sensors during the test is not available, the final positions were measured at the end of the tests and are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Initial and final location of pore-pressure transducers (relative to Figure 2)

Sensor	Initial Location		Final Test 1		Final Test 2		Final Test 3		Final Test 4	
	x (cm)	z (cm)	x (cm)	z (cm)	x (cm)	z (cm)	x (cm)	z (cm)	x (cm)	z (cm)
PPT_1	17.5	25	19.8	21.6	19.3	22.6	22.9	23.1	23.4	21.1
PPT_2	17.5	17.5	17.5	15.7	20.7	16.4	20.6	15.7	21.3	13.9
PPT_3	35	21	37.8	20.3	38.3	23.1	37.8	22.4	36.8	19.2
PPT_4	35	13.5	35.5	12.6	35.5	13.6	36	13.8	35.1	10.8
PPT_5	60	17.5	60.6	16.7	60.2	19	Not Available		60.5	15.5

3 Test 1 (Container 1)

3.1 General Overview

The main goal of Test 1 was to perform monotonic loading of the embankment under a drained loading condition and serve as a preliminary experiment for the remaining experimental campaign of SURE. A general description of the experiment based on Figure 3 is shown in Table 5, including the data file containing the information of each stage and the frames folder obtained during each stage, if any. It is noted that a short period without recording data occurred during the transition between stages. Nonetheless, such a period was generally lower than 120 seconds. Furthermore, the frame records typically start simultaneously with data recording, but they do not end at the same time.

Table 5 Experimental protocol on Test 1

Stage No.	Approx. Duration	Data File (ASCII)	Sampling Rate	Frames File (BMP)	Frame Rate
1 (without ballast load)	3.05 hrs	C1_conso	10 samp/sec	consolidation	1 frame/min
CPT_1	471.1 sec	C1CPT1	10 samp/sec		
2	Not performed				
3	3,11 hrs	C1_drained	10 samp/sec	C1 drainé chargement	1 frame/sec
CPT_2	470.7 sec	C1CPT2	10 samp/sec	Not available/not recorded	
CPT_3	652.5 sec	C1CPT3	10 samp/sec		

Stage 1 consisted of a self-weight consolidation lasting nearly three hours after reaching the target g -level of $20g$. It is noted that no ballast load was considered for this test. An initial CPT_1 was performed below the clay surface on the free field. Stage 3 consisted of increasing F_A until failure at variable controlled displacement rates ranging between 0.001 to 0.1 mm/s. Lastly, CPT_2 and CPT_3 were performed near the toe and at the crest of the embankment. Stage 2 was not performed as part of this test. Further details of Test 1 are included in this section.

3.2 Evolution of F_A , $d_{L,R}$, and Pore-water pressures

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the loading force, F_A , the loading plate displacement, d_A , d_L and d_R , and the pore pressures, PPT_2 through PPT_5 , measured during Test 1. The blue background highlights Stage 1, while the red background highlights the final monotonic loading performed at Stage 3. Stage 2 was not performed as part of this test. The initial decreasing tendency in the value of F_A corresponds to the initial spin-up sequence of the centrifuge to the target $20g$, followed by the self-weight consolidation time until nearly 200 minutes. Afterwards, the load plate was lowered to perform the monotonic loading sequence. It is noted that the loading plate inclined as the test advanced, which resulted in slightly different readings on d_L and d_R . In addition, the pore pressure measurements are presented as obtained during tests and without any preliminary correction based on the initial and final position of the sensors.

Figure 4 Evolution of load, displacements, and pore pressures during Test 1.

3.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing

Figure 5 shows the location of cone penetration tests and vane shear tests performed in Test 1. CPT tests used a 12-mm-diameter cone and were performed to a depth of approximately 250 mm below the initial clay surface. The CPT readings are presented in Figure 6. The vane shear tests were performed using a four-blade vane with a length of 50 mm and a width of 33 mm, attached to a steel rod. Locations for vane shear testing were 70 mm from the backwall of the model and 50, 220, 445 and 700 mm from the leftmost end. The testing depths were 40-90 mm, 125-175 mm, and 200-250 mm below the post-failure clay surface. Table 7 indicates the readings from vane shear tests on Test 4.

Table 6 Locations of CPTs

CPT	Plan Coordinate	
	x (mm)	y (mm)
C1CPT1	640	280
C1CPT2	325	280
C1CPT3	470	280

Figure 5 CPT and Vane Shear Testing (approximate) locations during Test 1.

Table 7 Results of Vane Shear Tests on Test 1

Plan Coordinate		Reading in kPa at depth:		
x (mm)	y (mm)	40-90 mm	125-175 mm	200-250 mm
50	70	13,73	16,48	13,73
220	70	13,73	13,64	Not available
445	70	14,52	14,81	14,52
700	70	15,70	16,78	16,87

The CPT profiles obtained in Test 1 show a good agreement, as shown in Figure 6. C1CPT2 was taken through the top sand layer and showed a peak at shallower depths.

Figure 6 Raw data of CPTs of Test 1.

3.4 Failure Mechanism

The surface profile of the clay was determined after the test by utilizing the top of the strongbox as reference height. The vertical distance to the top of the strongbox was measured in three alignments along the width of the strongbox by using a ruler. Figure 7 illustrates the measured surface profile of Test 1. The imprint made by the loading plate is noticeable in this figure. The locations of the CPT tests are also indicated as reference for the model layering.

Figure 7 Post-test clay surface profile after Test 1.

Figure 8 shows the failure plane that occurred during the Test 1. The indicative location of the embankment is shown by the dotted yellow line. The first failure mechanism that occurred was the punching of the clay. This is shown by failure line 1 (blue line). After increasing the load, a slip plane occurred, this is shown by failure line 2. The depth of the slip plane is at the boundary of the 2 consolidation layers. The figure shows the slip plane came up at the end of the embankment.

Failure plane test 1 - drained

Figure 8 Sketch of failure mechanism observed in Test 1.

4 Test 2 (Container 2)

4.1 General Overview

The main goal of Test 2 was to perform fully undrained monotonic loading of the embankment until failure. A general description of the experiment based on Figure 3 is shown in Table 8, including the data file containing the information of each stage and the frames folder obtained during each stage, if any. It is noted that a short period without recording data occurred during the transition between stages. Nonetheless, such a period was generally lower than 120 seconds. Furthermore, the frame records typically start simultaneously with data recording, but they do not end at the same time.

Table 8 Experimental protocol on Test 2

Stage No.	Approx. Duration	Data File (ASCII)	Sampling Rate	Frames File (BMP)	Frame Rate
1	8.10 hrs	C2_conso	10 samp/sec	consolidation	1 frame/min
CPT_1	Not available	C2CPT1	10 samp/sec		
2	Not performed				
3	551.8 sec	C2_undrained	200 samp/sec	undrained loading	2 frames/sec
CPT_2	1274.3 sec	C2CPT2	10 samp/sec	Not available/not recorded	
CPT_3	1229.4 sec	C2CPT3	10 samp/sec		
CPT_4	885.1 sec	C2CPT4	10 samp/sec		

Stage 1 consisted of a consolidation phase, including the ballast load. This stage was maintained for nearly eight hours after reaching the target g -level of $20g$. An initial CPT_1 was performed below the clay surface on the free field. However, CPT_1 was not considered representative due to a plastic covering the model's surface, which was pushed down during probing. Stage 3 consisted of increasing F_A until failure at constant controlled displacement rates of 0.35 mm/s. Lastly, CPT_2 through CPT_4 were performed at the free field, near the toe and at the crest of the embankment. Stage 2 was not performed as part of this test. Further details of Test 2 are included in this section.

4.2 Evolution of F_A , $d_{L,R}$, and Pore-water pressures

Figure 9 shows the evolution of the loading force, F_A , the loading plate displacement, d_A , d_L and d_R , and the pore pressures, PPT_2 through PPT_5 , measured during Test 2. The moment when the loading plate was in complete contact with the embankment was used as time $t=0$ min for this figure, which also indicated the onset of Stage 1 for this test (see Figure 3). The blue background highlights Stage 1, while the red background highlights the final monotonic loading performed at Stage 3. Stage 2 was not performed as part of this test. It is noted that the loading plate inclined as the tests advanced, which resulted in slightly different readings on d_L and d_R . In addition, the pore pressure measurements are presented as obtained during tests and without any preliminary correction based on the initial and final position of the sensors.

Figure 9 Evolution of load, displacements, and pore pressures during Test 2.

4.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing

Figure 10 shows the location of cone penetration tests and vane shear tests performed in Test 2. CPT tests used a 12-mm-diameter cone and were performed to a depth of approximately 250 mm below the initial clay surface. As can be seen, the order of the CPTs most likely not correct. C2CPT2 was taken through the embankment (Figure 10) whereas C2CPT3 shows the characteristics of a sand layer at the top of the CPT. Also C2CPT3 seems to have an offset of approximately 0.6 to 0.7 daN compared to the other two CPTs (Figure 11).

Table 9 Locations of CPTs

CPT	Plan Coordinate	
	x (mm)	y (mm)
C2CPT1	580	280
C2CPT2	350	280
C2CPT3	470	280
C2CPT4	575	280

Figure 10 CPT and Vane Shear Testing (approximate) locations during Test 2.

The vane shear tests were performed using a four-blade vane with a length of 50 mm and a width of 33 mm, attached to a steel rod. As for Test 1, the locations for vane shear testing were 70 mm from the backwall of the model and 50, 220, 445 and 700 mm from the leftmost end. The testing depths were 40-90 mm, 125-175 mm, and 200-250 mm below the post-failure clay surface. Table 10 indicates the readings from vane shear tests on Test 2.

Table 10 Results of Vane Shear Tests on Test 2

Plan Coordinate		Reading in kPa at depth:		
x (mm)	y (mm)	40-90 mm	125-175 mm	200-250 mm
50	70	12,26	15,21	15,40
220	70	12,26	15,01	16,78
445	70	11,77	14,13	14,81
700	70	12,02	15,79	15,01

Figure 11 RAW CPT readings in Test 2.

4.4 Failure Mechanism

The surface profile of the clay was determined after the test by utilizing the top of the strongbox as reference height. The vertical distance to the top of the strongbox was measured in three alignments along the width of the strongbox by using a ruler. Figure 12 illustrates the measured surface profile of Test 2.

Figure 13 shows the failure plane observed at the end of Test 2. The failure mechanism that occurred during the undrained test is a deep slip plane, which is represented by failure line 1. The depth of the slip plane is at the boundary of layers 1 and 3. Figure 13 also shows that the slip plane came up near the toe of the embankment, and other small displacements in horizontal and diagonal directions were caused by the undrained loading. This is shown by the multiple red lines. Figure 14 shows additional sketches of the failure plane identified preliminary at the end of Test 2.

Figure 12 Surface profile measurements for Test 2.

Failure plane test 2 - undrained

Figure 13 Sketch of failure mechanism observed in Test 2.

Figure 14 Preliminary failure plane after undrained loading in Test 2: Initial condition (top) and end of Test 2 (bottom).

5 Test 3 (Container 3)

5.1 General Overview

The main goal of Test 3 was to study the behaviour of the railway embankment system under different combinations of cyclic loading, with a constant frequency resembling a 10-minute passage interval in the prototype condition (see Figure 1) and a variable load amplitude. The cyclic loading was followed by a fully undrained monotonic loading until failure. A general description of the experiment on the basis of Figure 3 is shown in Table 11, including the data file containing the information on each stage and the frames folder obtained during each stage, if any. It is noted that a short period of time without recording data occurred during the transition between stages. Nonetheless, such a period was generally lower than 120 seconds. Furthermore, the frame records typically start simultaneously with data recording, but they do not end at the same time.

Table 11 Experimental protocol on Test 3

Stage No.	Approx. Duration	Data File (ASCII)	Sampling Rate	Frames File (BMP)	Frame Rate
1	2.3 hrs	C3_loading1	100 samp/sec	C3 consolidation	1 frame/min
2	2177 sec	C3_loading1	100 samp/sec		
	3.3 hrs	C3_loading2	300 samp/sec	C3 loading 30 kPa	2 frames/sec
	2.6 hrs	C3_loading 3	300 samp/sec	C3 loading 30 kPa bis	1 frame/min
CPT_1	393.0 sec	C3CPT1	300 samp/sec		
3	3096 sec	C3_loading_final	300 samp/sec	C3 final loading	2 frames/sec
CPT_2	493.3 sec	C3CPT2	300 samp/sec	Not available/not recorded	
CPT_3	398.6 sec	C3CPT3	300 samp/sec		

*Additional frames (0.5 fps) were recorded at “C3 1ere montée en g” during centrifuge balance pre-check

Stage 1 consisted of a consolidation phase, including the ballast load. This stage was maintained for nearly 2.3 hours after reaching the target g -level of $20g$. Stage 2 included 14400 cycles, as described in Table 12 and Figure 15. An initial CPT_1 was later performed below the clay surface on the free field. Stage 3 was performed by increasing F_A until failure at a constant controlled displacement rate of 0.35 mm/s. Lastly, CPT_2 and CPT_3 were performed near the toe and at the crest of the embankment. Further details of Test 3 are included in this section.

5.1.1 Cyclic Loading Sequences

In the project SURE, a single cycle was considered as the combination of two phases: first, a loading phase where the train arrives, crosses, and leaves the control section, and a standby phase with no train loading. Each cycle has a total duration of 10 or 4 minutes, depending on the condition assessed.

As indicated in section 2.2, a scaling for the time of $t = N^{-2}$ was used in the design of the experiments for SURE, where N is the increment in the gravitational acceleration field simulated in the centrifuge models. Figure 15 shows a sketch of a single cycle imposed to the models resembling train passages every 10 minutes in the prototype scale. The total duration of the cycle is 1.5 seconds in the model scale, the duration of the first phase is 0.37 seconds, and the duration of the second phase is 1.13 seconds. It is also noted that the minimum load is constant and equivalent to the ballast load.

Table 12 shows the load amplitudes, A , and the number of cycles used in the different loading sequences performed as part of Stage 2 on Test 3.

Figure 15 Template of load cycle in model scale resembling a 10-minute interval in prototype

Table 12 Load amplitudes and total number of cycles used in Test 3

Sequence No.	A (N)	Total Cycles	Data File (ASCII)	Sequential Execution ^a
1	1350	1200	C3_loading1	1-1-8-90-1100
2	2025	600	C3_loading2	1-1-8-90-500
3	2295	100		Continuous
4	2565	100		
5	2835	100		
6	3105	100		
7	3375	100		
8	3645	100		6000
9	3308	6000	C3_loading3	6000
10	3308	6000		

^a A short pause was allowed between cycles on the sequence

5.2 Evolution of F_A , $d_{L,R}$, and Pore-water pressures

Figure 16 shows the evolution of the loading force, F_A , the loading plate displacement, d_A , d_L and d_R , and the pore pressures, PPT_2 through PPT_5 , measured during Test 3.

Figure 16 Evolution of load, displacements, and pore pressures during Test 3.

The moment when the loading plate was in complete contact with the embankment was used as time $t=0$ min for Figure 16, which also indicated the onset of Stage 1 for this test (see Figure 3). The blue background highlights Stage 1, while the green background highlights the cyclic loading stage modelling 10-minute passages. The red background highlights the final monotonic loading performed at Stage 3. It is noted that the loading plate inclined as the tests advanced, which resulted in slightly different readings on d_L and d_R . In addition, the pore pressure measurements are presented as obtained during tests and without any preliminary correction based on the initial and final position of the sensors. As such, pore pressures at PPT_1 and portions of PPT_2 during the cyclic loading are not included in Figure 16c due to extensive noise on signals.

5.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing

Figure 17 shows the location of cone penetration tests and vane shear tests performed in Test 3. CPT tests used a 12-mm-diameter cone and were performed to a depth of approximately 250 mm below the initial clay surface. Figure 18 shows the readings of the CPTs. In the top figure all readings at 300 Hz are presented, showing the accuracy of the measurements. In the bottom figure the readings have been averaged over 100 readings, resulting in a 3Hz signal. The vane shear tests were performed using a four-blade vane with a length of 50 mm and a width of 33 mm, attached to a steel rod. Locations for vane shear testing were 70 mm from the backwall of the model, and 50, 190, 440 and 530 mm from the leftmost end. The testing depths were 40-90 mm, 100-150 mm, and 200-250 mm below the post-failure clay surface. Table 13 indicates the readings from vane shear tests on Test 4.

Table 13 Results of Vane Shear Tests on Test 3

Plan Coordinate		Reading in kPa at depth:		
x (mm)	y (mm)	40-90 mm	100-150 mm	200-250 mm
50	70	11,18	14,62	15,40
190	70	14,91	16,87	16,87
440	70	15,01	17,66	16,19
530	70	17,66	16,78	17,56

Table 14 Locations of CPTs

CPT	Plan Coordinate	
	x (mm)	y (mm)
C3CPT1	675	280
C3CPT2	465	250
C3CPT3	350	160

Figure 17 CPT and Vane Shear Testing (approximate) locations during Test 3.

Figure 18 Raw data CPT readings in Test 3, top figure with 300Hz and bottom figure with 3Hz readings.

5.4 Failure Mechanism

The model's surface was scanned using a laser sensor to estimate surface profiles after Test 3, including the overall final elevation across the width of the model, and the final surface of the clay layer towards the middle section of the model, as shown in Figure 19. In this figure, the elevation $z = 0$ cm corresponds to the approximated initial clay surface. Three sections along the length of the model (i.e., x-axis) were scanned at distances of 8.2 cm, 22.3 cm, and 29.8 from the front (i.e., y-axis). In the case of the final overall surface of the model, each section comprised three subsections to accommodate the limited scanning length of the laser setup. For the final surface of the clay later, only one subsection was scanned. It is noted that a surface profile for the initial conditions was not available for this experiment, but it was approximated.

Data shown in Figure 19 can be accessed from the data files in folder C3_Surface_Maps, which includes the individual files per section as described above, each containing z and x values for each subsection.

Figure 19 Surface profiles on Test 3: (a) 29.8 cm, (b) 22.3 cm, and (c) 8.2 cm from the front section.

Figure 20 presents a preliminary comparison by superimposing selected images to highlight the evolution of Test 3. Figures (a) and (b) compare the initial conditions with the end of Stage 1: Consolidation (refer to Figure 3). Figures (c) and (d) compare the end of Stage 1: Consolidation with the end of Stage 2: Cyclic Loading, while Figures (e) and (f) compare the end of Stage 2: Cyclic Loading with the final failure of the model after the test. The green and magenta colors in Figures (a), (c), and (e) represent the original and final conditions, respectively, for each comparison. In contrast, Figures (b), (d), and (f) highlight the areas of greatest difference identified in each case.

Test 3 Evolution

Figure 20 Image comparison of events during Test 3: (a, b) Initial conditions vs. end of Stage1; (c,d) end of Stage 1 vs. end of Stage 2; and (e,f) end of Stage 2 vs. end of Stage 3.

5.6 Additional Measurements

This section includes the additional information obtained as part of Test 3, including water contents measurements at the end of the experiment.

5.6.1 Post-failure water contents on Speswhite kaolin

Estimations of water content for the foundation layers at the end of the experiment were obtained by extruding a column of soil using a 5.0-cm-diameter pipe. The probing location was 680 mm and 360 mm on the x- and y-planes, respectively (see Figure 17). The pipe was pushed in from the post-failure clay surface up to an approximate depth of 253 mm, and it was later cut into several sections and oven-dried for water content estimations. Table 15 shows the final measurements obtained.

Table 15 Post-failure water contents on foundation layer in Test 3 (sampling depths not reported).

Sample ID	w_c (%)
10 (Surface)	44,92
9	40,67
8	45,49
7	46,23
6	53,52
5	46,31
4	45,90
3	46,41
2	46,14
1 (Bottom of Probing)	46,62

6 Test 4 (Container 4)

6.1 General Overview

The main goal of Test 4 was to study the behaviour of the railway embankment system under different combinations of cyclic loading, including the transition from a constant frequency resembling a 10-minute passage interval in the prototype condition (see Figure 1) to a 4-minute passage interval. In both cases, various load amplitudes were considered. The cyclic loading was followed by a fully undrained monotonic loading until failure. A general description of the experiment based on Figure 3 is shown in Table 16, including the data file containing the information on each stage and the frames folder obtained during each stage, if any. It is noted that a short period without recording data occurred during the transition between stages. Nonetheless, such a period was generally lower than 120 seconds. Furthermore, the frame records typically start simultaneously with data recording, but they do not end at the same time.

Table 16 Experimental protocol on Test 4

Stage No.	Approx. Duration	Data File (ASCII)	Sampling Rate	Frames File (BMP)	Frame Rate
1	2.2 hrs	C4_conso	300 samp/sec	C4 consolidation	1 frame/min
<i>CPT</i> ₁	439.4 sec	C4CPT1	300 samp/sec		
2	3.9 hrs	C4_first_loading	300 samp/sec	C4 loading 1	1 frame/sec
	2.7 hrs	C4_second_loading	300 samp/sec		
3	1357 sec	C4_final_loading	300 samp/sec	C4 final loading	2 frames/sec
<i>CPT</i> ₂	462.1 sec	C4CPT2	300 samp/sec	Not available/not recorded	
<i>CPT</i> ₃	373.5 sec	C4CPT3	300 samp/sec		
<i>CPT</i> ₄	439.4 sec	C4CPT4	300 samp/sec		

Stage 1 consisted of a consolidation phase including the ballast load. This stage was maintained for nearly 2.15 hours after reaching the target g -level of $20g$. An initial *CPT*₁ was performed below the clay surface on the free field. Stage 2 included nearly 23,500 cycles as described on Table 17 and Figure 21. Then, Stage 3 was performed by increasing F_A until failure at a constant controlled displacement rate of 0.35 mm/s. Lastly, *CPT*₂ through *CPT*₄ were performed near the toe and at the crest of the embankment. Further details of Test 4 are included in this section.

6.1.1 Cyclic Loading Sequences

As indicated in section 5.1.1, a single cycle was considered as the combination of two phases: first, a loading phase where the train arrives, crosses, and leaves the control section; and second, a standby phase with no train loading. Each cycle has a total duration of 10 or 4 minutes depending on the condition assessed.

As indicated in section 2.2, a scaling for time of $t = N^{-2}$ was used in the design of the experiments for SURE, where N is the increment in the gravitational acceleration field simulated in the centrifuge models. Figure 21 shows sketches of the cycles imposed on the models resembling train passages every 10 minutes and 4 minutes in the prototype scale. The duration of the first phase is 0.37 seconds regardless of the total duration of the cycle, and the duration of the second phase is 1.13 seconds for the 10 minute case, and 0.23 seconds for the 4 minute case. It is also noted that the minimum load is constant and equivalent to the ballast load.

Figure 21 Template of load cycles in model scale resembling: (a) 10-minute interval, and (b) 4-minute interval in prototype

Table 17 shows the load amplitudes, A , and the number of cycles used in the different loading sequences performed as part of Stage 2 on Test 4. It is highlighted that the sequences 1 through 8, and the first 3,000 cycles on sequence 9 were performed in both Tests 3 and 4 to replicate a similar stress history in both models.

Table 17 Load amplitudes and total number of cycles used in Test 4

Sequence No.	A (N)	Total Cycles	Cycle Duration Model (Prototype)	Data File (ASCII)	Sequential Execution ^a
1	1350	1200	1.5 sec (10 min)	C4_first_loading	Continuous
2	2025	600			
3	2295	100			
4	2565	100			
5	2835	100			
6	3105	100			
7	3375	100			
8	3645	100			
9	3308	3000	0.6 sec (4 min)	C4_second_loading	500 – 3500 – 3500
10	3308	7500			Continuous
11	4000	100			100 – 2900
12	4300	3000	1.5 sec (10 min)	C4_second_loading	500 – 3500 – 3500
13	4300	7500			

^a A short pause was allowed between cycles on the sequence

6.2 Evolution of F_A , $d_{L,R}$, and Pore-water pressures

Figure 22 shows the evolution of the loading force, F_A , the loading plate displacement, d_A , d_L and d_R , and the pore pressures, PPT_1 through PPT_5 , measured during Test 4. The moment when the loading plate was in complete contact with the embankment was used as time $t=0$ min for this figure, which also indicated the onset of Stage 1 for this test (see Figure 3). The blue background highlights Stage 1, while green and yellow backgrounds highlight the cyclic loading stages modelling 10-minute and 4-minute train passages, respectively. The red background highlights the final monotonic loading performed at Stage 3. It is noted that the loading plate inclined as the tests advanced, which

resulted in slightly different readings on d_L and d_R . In addition, the pore pressure measurements are presented as obtained during tests and without any preliminary correction based on the initial and final position of the sensors.

Figure 22 Evolution of load, displacements, and pore pressures during Test 4.

6.3 CPT and Vane Shear Testing

Figure 23 shows the location of cone penetration tests and vane shear tests performed in Test 4. CPT tests used a 12-mm-diameter cone and were performed to a depth of approximately 250 mm below the initial clay surface. Figure 18 shows the CPT readings for test 4. As for the third test, the top figure of Figure 18 shows all the measured data at 300 Hz. This gives an insight into the accuracy of the measurements. In the bottom figure, the data was averaged over 100 readings, resulting in a 3Hz signal. As for the second test, there is an offset in the cone resistance for the CPT that was taken in the embankment, although less pronounced as for test 2 (approximately 0.4 to 0.5 daN).

The vane shear tests were performed using a four-blade vane with a length of 50 mm and a width of 33 mm, attached to a steel rod. Locations for vane shear testing were 70 mm from the backwall of the model and 50, 210, 420 and 530 mm from the leftmost end. The testing depths were 40-90 mm, 100-150 mm, and 200-250 mm below the post-failure clay surface. Table 19 indicates the readings from vane shear tests on Test 4.

Table 18 Locations of CPTs

CPT	Plan Coordinate	
	x (mm)	y (mm)
C4CPT1	660	200
C4CPT2	580	220
C4CPT3	450	220
C4CPT4	345	275

Figure 23 CPT and Vane Shear Testing (approximate) locations during Test 4.

Table 19 Results of Vane Shear Tests on Test 4

Plan View Coordinates		Reading in kPa at depth:		
x (mm)	y (mm)	40-90 mm	100-150 mm	200-250 mm
50	70	11,87	12,85	16,68
210	70	15,60	17,07	17,76
420	70	15,70	14,81	17,76
530	70	17,17	17,56	17,71

Figure 24 Raw data CPT readings in Test 4, top figure with 300Hz and bottom figure with 3Hz readings.

6.4 Failure Mechanism

The surface of the model was scanned using a laser sensor to estimate surface profiles before and after Test 4, including overall initial and final elevations, and the final surface of the clay layer, as shown in Figure 25. In this figure, the elevation $z = 0$ cm corresponds to the approximated initial clay surface. A total of three sections along the length of the model (i.e., x-axis) were scanned at distances of 8.2 cm, 22.3 cm, and 29.8 from the front (i.e., y-axis). In the

case of the initial and final overall surface of the model, each section comprised three subsections to accommodate the limited scanning length of the laser setup. For the final surface of the clay later, only one subsection was scanned.

Data shown in Figure 25 can be accessed from the data files in folder C4_Surface_Maps, which includes the individual files per section as described above, each containing z and x values for each subsection.

Figure 25 Surface profiles on Test 4: (a) 29.8 cm, (b) 22.3 cm, and (c) 8.2 cm from the front section.

Figure 26 presents a preliminary comparison by superimposing selected images to highlight the evolution of Test 4. Figures (a) and (b) compare the initial conditions with the end of Stage 1: Consolidation (refer to Figure 3). Figures (c) and (d) compare the end of Stage 1: Consolidation with the end of Stage 2: Cyclic Loading, while Figures (e) and (f) compare the end of Stage 2: Cyclic Loading with the final failure of the model after the test. The green and magenta colors in Figures (a), (c), and (e) represent the original and final conditions, respectively, for each comparison. In contrast, Figures (b), (d), and (f) highlight the areas of greatest difference identified in each case.

Test 4 Evolution

Figure 26 Image comparison of events during Test 4: (a, b) Initial conditions vs. end of Stage1; (c,d) end of Stage 1 vs. end of Stage 2; and (e,f) end of Stage 2 vs. end of Stage 3.

6.5 Additional Measurements

This section includes the additional information obtained as part of Test 4, including water contents measurements at the end of the experiment and estimations of the evolution of the temperature during the duration of the centrifuge flight.

6.5.1 Post-failure water contents of Speswhite kaolin

Estimations of water content for the foundation layers at the end of the experiment were obtained by extruding a column of soil using a 5.0-cm-diameter pipe. The probing location was 680 mm and 360 mm on the x- and y-planes, respectively (see Figure 23). The pipe was pushed in from the post-failure clay surface up to an approximate depth of 253 mm, and it was later cut into several sections and oven-dried for water content estimations. Table 20 shows the final measurements obtained.

Table 20 Post-failure water contents on foundation layer in Test 4

Average Depth of Sampling (cm)	w_c (%)
0,55	46,88
2,55	48,15
5,50	44,83
8,55	43,86
11,60	45,61
14,60	45,76
17,65	44,07
20,60	41,82
23,65	47,62

6.5.2 Temperature evolution during flight on Test 4

To assess the possible effects of temperature changes during flight, a temperature probe was placed nearly 2 mm below the initial clay surface on the free-field section of the model. Figure 27 shows the evolution of the temperature experienced during the development of Test 4. Temperature data on this figure is available on channel “Temp CH=16”, as indicated in Table 3, and for all the data files in Table 16. It is highlighted that the temperatures shown in Figure 27 should not be assumed representative of Tests 1 and 2 since considerable changes in ambient temperature occurred between the execution of both experimental campaigns, as indicated in Figure 28.

Figure 27 Evolution of temperature near clay surface on Test 4

Figure 28 Temperature and weather conditions during the two test weeks (source: <https://www.timeanddate.com/>).